

Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) for Operation of the IPCC Data Distribution Centre

29 October 2021

Presented at IPCC TG-Data F2F 2021 Meeting, 22 October 2021

1. Objectives of the MoU

1. Set out the framework for joint operation of the IPCC Data Distribution Centre (DDC), to enable efficient collaboration among the partners;
2. Create transparency about roles and responsibilities, and provide a mechanism for managing roles, identifying gaps, and allocating resources.

2. History of the DDC

The initiative to establish a mechanism for dissemination of data grew out of discussions on establishment of the Task Group on Climate Scenarios for Impact Assessment (TGICIA) at the IPCC Workshop on Regional Climate Change Projections for Impact Assessment (London, 24-26 September 1996). This Task Group was formed at a Preliminary Planning Meeting (Bracknell, 9-10 January 1997). The recommendation to establish a Data Distribution Centre was formulated at this meeting and led to the decision on the First TGICIA Meeting (Washington, 5-6 May 1997) to seek Bureau approval for a request for governments to provide the necessary financial support to establish and maintain the DDC function. Governments were invited by an IPCC letter (22 July 1997) to nominate institutions to act as the DDC.

The IPCC Data Distribution Centre (DDC) was formally established by the decisions at the IPCC Bureau 14th Session (Maldives, 21 September 1997) and at the 13th IPCC Plenary (Maldives, 22-28 September 1997). An Ad-Hoc Committee on the Data Distribution Centre was formed to identify institutions for the DDC. Among several institutions nominated by governments, Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ) in Germany and the Climatic Research Unit (CRU) in the United Kingdom were selected as a shared DDC operation.

The DDC was overseen by the IPCC TGICIA, which was renamed to the Task Group on Data and Scenario Support for Impact and Climate Analysis (TGICA) in 2003. The governance of the DDC was reviewed by an Ad-Hoc task force in 2017/18, resulting in revised guidance and objectives adopted at 47th IPCC Plenary (Paris, 13-16 March 2018): new [Terms of Reference](#) for the Task Group renamed in Task Group on Data Support for Climate Change Assessments (TG-Data) and new [Guidance for the core functions of the DDC](#).

Between 2000 and 2009, the German DDC was operated by the Model and Data Group of the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MaD/MPI-M). The Center for International Earth

Science Information Network (CIESIN) in the USA was invited to the Third TGICIA Meeting (New York, 15-17 May 2000) and to the 5th Meeting (Barbados, 26-29 November 2001) to develop socio-economic scenario data link to the DDC. CIESIN became a formal part of the DDC at the 6th TGICIA Meeting (Helsinki, 5-7 June 2002), which was reported to the 20th IPCC Plenary (Paris, 19-21 February 2003). British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC) was invited to the 12th TGICIA Meeting (Exeter, 4-6 October 2006) in place of CRU as the United Kingdom DDC partner, and formally joined the DDC at the 13th TGICIA Meeting (Nadi, 17-19 June 2007). BADC evolved its name to the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) in 2012. In 2019, Spanish Research Council - Instituto de Física de Cantabria (CSIC-IFCA) participated in the First TG-Data Meeting (Montreal, 6-8 November 2019), and joined the DDC in March 2021. Since June 2021, MetadataWorks has participated in DDC activities, and replaced CEDA as the United Kingdom DDC partner at the TG-Data F2F 2021 Meeting (22 October 2021).

3. Role and Responsibilities of the DDC

The roles and responsibilities of the DDC are set out by the [Guidance for the core functions of the IPCC Data Distribution Centre](#) (DDC) in Annex 2 of the report on the 47th Session of the IPCC Plenary ([Decision IPCC-XLVII-9](#)):

The DDC will, contingent on the availability of resources:

2.1 Archive and provide transparency, traceability, and stability of data and scenarios used by the IPCC in its reports, available at the DDC or elsewhere.

2.2 Archive and provide transparency, traceability, and stability of data and scenarios underpinning key figures and tables, and headline statements in the IPCC reports.

2.3 Collaborate as appropriate with data centers that hold data or provide functions relevant to the IPCC in a transparent manner, under the guidance of the TG-DATA and the Working Group Bureaus (WGBs), to provide information via IPCC websites relevant to data and scenarios.

2.4 Curate new data sets unavailable elsewhere and link to external data sets of relevance.

2.5 Improve accessibility to Data Distribution Centre materials for supporting IPCC authors and external users, especially in developing countries.

2.6 Contribute to a sustainable structure established and approved by the IPCC to provide observed and model data and information relevant at regional scales.

4. Undertakings of the Undersigned DDC Partners

- To support the roles and responsibilities of the DDC as set out by the IPCC 47th Plenary;
- To seek and deploy resources targeted at those roles and responsibilities;
- To establish and maintain a framework for efficient collaboration;
- To apply best practices in data curation to the IPCC datasets, and promote the best practices in the IPCC community, e.g., by core trustworthy data repositories and through coordination with the World Data System of the International Science Council (ISC-WDS).

5. Current Partners

- *German Climate Computing Centre (DKRZ)*

DKRZ (Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH) is a non-profit and non-commercial limited company. DKRZ provides central services for German climate and earth system research, and operates the World Data Center Climate (WDCC). DKRZ is a regular member of the ISC-WDS and joined the Coalition for Publishing Data in the Earth and Space Sciences (COPDESS).

Director: Thomas Ludwig

url: <http://www.dkrz.de> / <http://www.wdc-climate.de>

- *Center for International Earth Science Information Network (CIESIN)*

CIESIN (Center for International Earth Science Information Network) is part of the Columbia Climate School at Columbia University (New York, USA). CIESIN specializes in on-line data and information management, spatial data integration and training, and interdisciplinary research related to human interactions in the environment. CIESIN operates the U.S. NASA Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC), a regular member of the ISC-WDS.

Director: Robert S. Chen

url: <http://www.ciesin.columbia.edu/>

- *Spanish Research Council (CSIC)*

CSIC (Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas), Spain, is a public research body. PTI-Clima is a network of CSIC research centers working in climate coordinated by the Institute of Physics of Cantabria (IFCA) and is specialized in on-line data services and applications and cloud facilities for data analysis. CSIC is joining the federation for supporting the Interactive Atlas and related activities and will maintain its collaboration until June 2023 unless the Parties by mutual consent decide to extend its duration.

Head (Vice President for International Affairs): Ángeles Gómez Borrego

url: <http://www.csic.es> / <http://www.ifca.es>

- *MetadataWorks*

MetadataWorks Limited, based in Totnes, United Kingdom, is a software development and consultancy company that provides data management solutions to government agencies, corporations and research organisations.

Director: Adam Milward

url: <https://metadataworks.co.uk/>

6. Revisions of the MoU

- This MoU can be revised, including changes of DDC Partners, as requested by TG-Data;

- New DDC Partners should be approved by TG-Data after consultation with existing DDC Partners;
- New DDC Partners should be added to the MoU by adding signatures to addenda;
- Status changes of existing DDC Partners should be informed to TG-Data and other DDC Partners in a timely manner;
- DDC Partners that plan to stop supporting the DDC should inform TG-Data and other DDC Partners with as much advance warning as possible and should coordinate on appropriate transfer of capabilities and responsibilities.

7. Signatures

German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ)

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 D-20146 Hamburg, Germany

www.dkrz.de

Director: Thomas Ludwig

Signature:

Date: 01.11.2021

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Date: 29 October 2021

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METADATAWORKS

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 United Kingdom

metadataworks.co.uk

Director: Adam Milward

Signature:

Date:

1 December 2021

8. Annexes

References

1. IPCC 1997: Report of the 13th Session of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). Maldives, 22 & 25-28 September 1997.
<https://www.ipcc.ch/meetings/session13/thirteenth-session-report.pdf>
2. IPCC Bureau, session 14 (Maldives, 21st September 1997): report not published.
3. IPCC 2003: Report of the 20th Session of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC): IPCC-XX/Doc.11, Rev.1. Paris, 19-21 February 2003
<https://archive.ipcc.ch/meetings/session20/doc11rev1.pdf>
4. IPCC 2018: 47TH SESSION OF THE IPCC: Decisions adopted by the Panel, Paris, 13–16 March 2018: [Decision IPCC-XLVII-9](#)
5. ATF-TGICA 2018c: REPORT BY THE AD HOC TASK FORCE ON THE FUTURE OF THE TASK GROUP ON DATA AND SCENARIO SUPPORT FOR IMPACT AND CLIMATE ANALYSIS, 47th session of the IPCC. [IPCC-XLVII/Doc. 9](#)

Procedures for maintaining DDC web site content

Major changes (for example, redesign or reconstruction of the DDC website) should be reviewed and approved by all DDC Partners and TG-Data. Significant content changes and additions should be reported to TG-Data meetings.

The URL www.ipcc-data.org is the main portal to the DDC web site. The content can be split into four broad categories:

- **General pages**, describing the role and history of the DDC, linking to the MoU, etc.;
- **Dataset pages**, describing specific datasets and provide links to data files or to archive pages which in turn lead to the files;
- **Thematic pages**, providing detailed discussion of specific subject areas (e.g., a page describing the WGI interactive Atlas and the connection to IPCC DDC);
- **Guidance pages**, providing guidance on specific topics or linking to documents.